

Synthesis of carbon nanotubes using spinach, characterization and study of magnetic properties[†]

I. P. Tripathi^{a*}, B. Tiwari^b and Sanjay Saxena^c

^aFaculty of Science and Environment, Department of Physical Sciences,
Mahatma Gandhi Chitrakoot Gramodaya Vishwavidyalaya, Chitrakoot, Satna-485 001, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : tripathi.ip@gmail.com

^bDirector, Trident Group of Colleges, Morta, Meerut Road, Ghaziabad-201 003, Uttar Pradesh, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Shri Venkateshwara University, Gajraula-244 236, Dt. J. P. Nagar,
Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract : Nano Technology is growing at a faster pace and is leaving its impact on our day to day life. Nano materials are undoubtedly the most valuable resource in the development of this technology. So it is very essential to develop new methods to produce these materials. Keeping this view in mind CNTs were made by using protein present in spinach and metal ions as catalyst. The chemical compound, so formed was decomposed at different temperatures to obtain CNTs. These CNTs were characterized using SEM and Micro Raman spectroscopy.

Keywords : Carbon nanotubes, spinach, synthesis, characterization.

Introduction

Nanotechnology refers to a field of applied science and technology. The basic theme of this technology is to control the matter on the atomic and molecular scale, generally 100 nm or smaller, and the fabrication of devices or materials that lie within that size range, comes under that pervue of nano science and technology.

Nanotechnology is a highly multidisciplinary field; its basic roots are spread in the fields of applied physics, materials science, interface and colloid science, device physics, supramolecular chemistry, self-replicating machines and robotics, chemical engineering, mechanical engineering, biological engineering and electrical engineering^{1,2}.

Carbon nanotubes are molecular-scale tubes of graphitic carbon with outstanding properties. They are among the stiffest and strongest fibers known, and have remarkable electronic properties and many other unique charac-

teristics like high tensile strength, high thermal stability and magnetic behavior. Due to their unique characteristics development of new techniques to produce CNTs is the area of interest for so many researchers^{3,4}.

Experimental

For the production of CNTs high amount of carbon is required at a particular place so proteins are taken as key material to produce CNTs. Proteins is bio polymers of amino acids. Amino acids are compounds containing -NH₂ and COOH groups within a molecule, with the help of these groups amino acids form complexes with metals. In these complexes different chains of amino acids are combined together. These compounds on decomposition give carbon-metal nano tubes. Spinach has high protein content, though the percentage of protein varies in different varieties of spinach. It contains proteins like arginine, histidine, lysine and cystein. New protein spinach is also discovered from the leaves of spinach. So due to high

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

protein content of spinach, we decided to choose it for synthesis of CNTs.

5 ml of 1 N aqueous solution of nickel salt is allowed to react with amino acids of keratin protein present in spinach. For that purpose spinach is crushed and grinded. The lone pair present on nitrogen of $-NH_2$ and oxygen of COOH group present in amino acid form complex with Ni^{II} . In this way nickel(II) forms cross link between two amino acid chains. The sample is kept undisturbed in desiccators for some time for self precipitation and drying. It was observed that reaction is incomplete so the sample is heated for few minutes in the oven to complete the reaction.

The samples formed are decomposed at different temperatures (900 °C, 950 °C and 1200 °C) in a muffle furnace. At 1200 °C only soot is formed. The samples decomposed at 900 °C and 950 °C are characterized by scanning probe instruments⁵⁻⁷.

Results and discussion

Characterization by DLS :

DLS is dynamic light scattering it is also known as photon correlation spectroscopy it is a technique in physics and is used to determine the distribution profile of small particles in suspension. This technique is based on the scattering of light in all directions, after hitting small particles and time dependent fluctuation of small particles in the scattering intensity.

After decomposing the sample at different temperatures those samples were characterized by using DLS^{6,7}.

(i) Results of sample decomposed at 800 °C : In this sample the chemical compound is prepared by the reaction of protein and nickel salt solution is decomposed at 800 °C. The results are shown in the Fig. 1. From the above figure it is clear that crystals with particle size 10 to 100 nm are formed but they are very less in number.

(ii) Results of sample decomposed at 1000 °C : In this sample the chemical compound is prepared by the reaction of protein and nickel salt solution is decomposed at 1000 °C. The results are shown in the Fig. 2. In this figure the particles occupying nano dimension are more in number but degradation is also more.

Due to the above observations it was clear that we can get better results at a temperature of 900 °C and 950 °C. So the samples were again decomposed at 900 °C and 950 °C. DLS results are summed up in Tables 1 and 2.

Characterization using SEM :

SEM is Scanning Electron Microscopy. The sample was analyzed at Nano Center, Allahabad University the make and model of the instrument is SEMSEI QUANTA 200MK SERIES. It images a sample by scanning it with beam of electrons in a rectangular pattern. Electrons interact with the atoms that make up samples to produce signals; it gives information about the sample. Figs. 3 and 4 shows SEM images of CNTs formed at a decomposition temperature of 900 °C and 950 °C^{6,7}.

Characterization by Micro Raman Spectroscopy :

This technique is used to measure Raman spectra of microscopic samples or microscopic areas of big objects. It is a spectroscopic technique to study vibrational, rotational and other low frequency modes in a system. The sample was analyzed at Nano Center, Allahabad University the make and model of the instrument is RENISHAW.

In Raman spectroscopy sample is illuminated with a laser beam. With the help of lance light from illuminated spot is collected and passed through a monochromator. The wave length closed to the laser beam is filtered off and rest is passed through the detector. Raman spectroscopy is most probably the most reliable way to characterize CNTs^{11,12}. It gives us the idea whether the CNT formed is multi walled (fullerene) or single walled (grapheme).

In the graph which shown in Fig. 5, stock lines are observed in the spectrum in lower frequency range. Two bands are present in the Raman spectra of CNTs is that-

G BAND : G Band is a tangential spear mode of carbon atoms, which corresponds to stretching mode in the graphite plane. This band is clearly visible in the graph.

D BAND : This band is longitudinal optical phenomenon and is known as disorder or defect mode. It is usually located between 1330 and 1360 cm^{-1} . From the graph it is clear that the multi walled carbon nano tubes are formed.

Fig. 1. DLF results of sample decomposed at 800 °C.

Fig. 2. DLF results of sample decomposed at 1000 °C.

Study of magnetic properties :

The magnetic properties of CNTs are studied using VSM. VSM is vibrating sample magnetometer and is used to study magnetic behavior of magnetic materials. It works on the basis of Faraday's induction law. This law states, changing magnetic field produce electrical field.

In VSM technique sample is placed in constant mag-

netic field. If the sample is magnetic it will get magnetized and a magnetic couple is created by the magnetic dipole moment. This created magnetic couple is used to study the properties of CNTs¹⁰. CNTs are expected to show paramagnetic behavior. This behavior is due to the presence of unpaired electrons.

The magnetic moment of CNTs is compared using a

Table 1. DLS results

Record	Type	Sample name	Measurement date and time	T (°C)	Z-Ave d.nm	PdI	Pk1 Mean Int d.nm	Pk2 Mean Int d.nm	Pk3 Mean Int d.nm	Pk1 Area Int (%)	Pk2 Area Int (%)	Pk3 Area Int (%)
1	Size	1000c_S1	Monday, June 07, 2010 11:52	25.0	108.2	0.660	61.87	26.43	0.000	55.9	44.1	
2	Size	1000c_S2	Monday, June 07, 2010 11:55	25.0	105.1	0.515	73.74	39.93	0.000	71.3	28.7	
3	Size	1000c_S3	Monday, June 07, 2010 11:57	25.1	99.02	0.329	83.46	49.27	0.000	90.1	9.9	
4	Size	800c_S1	Monday, June 07, 2010 12:02	25.0	572.2	0.461	86.75	19.63	0.000	92.5	7.5	
5	Size	800c_S2	Monday, June 07, 2010 12:05	25.0	206.7	1.000	23.42	37.79	0.000	77.8	22.2	
6	Size	800c_S3	Monday, June 07, 2010 12:08	25.0	153.5	1.000	32.64	43.02	228.4	62.1	29.6	

Table 2. DLS results

Peak 3 area intensity (%)	Mean count rate keps	Multimodal fit error	Cumulants fit error	Number mean d.nm	Volume mean d.nm
0.0	178.5	0.00369	9.58e-4	55.50	1090
0.0	176.8	0.00157	4.98e-4	60.41	1576
0.0	156.2	0.00208	6.81e-4	63.73	995.5
0.0	200.4	0.00835	0.0238	19.15	388.3
0.0	186.1	0.00697	0.00857	35.63	1006
8.2	171.7	0.00505	0.00705	40.61	1417

Fig. 3. SEM pictures of CNTs at 900 °C.

Fig. 4. SEM pictures of CNTs at 950 °C.

blank reference. In blank sample the magnetic moment of the instrument is studied against magnetic field. Then the experiment is repeated by taking 0.0057 g of sample. The graphs of blank and sample between magnetic moment and magnetic field are shown in Figs. 6 and 7.

Conclusion :

In the light of above results it is clear that CNTs can be produced by the reaction of protein present in spinach with metal and decomposing the compounds formed. These CNTs have unpaired electrons and are paramagnetic in nature. Due to the presence of unpaired electrons they are also expected to show electrical and thermal conductance.

Fig. 5. Raman spectra of CNTs.

Fig. 6. VSM graphs of (a) blank.

Fig. 7. VSM graphs of (b) sample.

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